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by

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SUMMARY <i>The high-resolution HYCOM model of the Nordic Seas has been nested into the TOPAZ system in free running mode and integrated for the years 2007-2009. The year 2008 is kept for analysis and validation. The model validation is conducted against satellite SST and in-situ temperature and salinity profiles.</i>	
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REPORT TEXT

Introduction

This work is the Work Package 1 of the Norwegian Research Council funded project "Ocean weather and ecosystem in the Nordic seas - a Norwegian component to the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS)". The principle objectives and sub-goals are:

To further build on our competence in "operational oceanography" focusing on basic research:

- For improving and validating our TOPAZ system nested for the Nordic Seas and key Norwegian coastal regions.
- To implement and validate a new formulation for the ecosystem of the Nordic Seas.
- To incorporate measurements of the internal ocean and biochemical variability.
- To design and assess a cost effective configuration of a Nordic Seas network of observations.
- To demonstrate the improved TOPAZ modelling and data assimilation system in operation over a period of one year and compare the output with other existing operational products.

The report continues the work initiated by Nina Winther in 2005 (initial model set up with HYCOM v2.1 on the HPC Njord at NTNU, Trondheim and examination of a 3-month simulation) and Cecilie Hansen in 2008 (upgrade to HYCOM 2.2 and porting to the HPC Hexagon at Parallab, Bergen), it covers the model setup and the validation of one year of model simulation (2008) from the HYCOM eddy-resolving model of the Nordic Seas (NORDIC) nested into the TOPAZ4 system. The validation data encompass satellite SST data and hydrographic in-situ data. Two months have been extracted, February which is typical of winter conditions and July for summer conditions. The model simulation is intended to contribute one chapter to a book on the oceanography of the Nordic Seas, the validation also concentrates on the water mass properties on the East Greenland Sea and especially in the Irminger Sea for the purpose of studying the influence of an ocean warming on the Greenland ice sheet.

The report does not cover the other WPs of the project like the coupling to ecosystem models and data assimilation although consequent work have been carried on these questions within the projects eVITA-EnKF (eVITA), ACUSAT (HavKyst) and the EU projects MyOcean that contribute to the modeling and assimilation system. The assistance of A. Korablev, A. Korosov and P. Sakov for providing quality-checked data and Matlab routines is warmly acknowledged.

Figure 1: NORDIC 4 km model bottom topography (meters), nesting conditions from the TOPAZ4 system are applied to the Northern and Southern boundaries.

Model Setup

The overall model system consists of a nested system, where the large scale TOPAZ4 model provides nesting conditions to a regional Nordic Seas HYCOM model, see Figure 1. TOPAZ4 has a horizontal resolution of 10 – 16 km, while the Nordic Seas model has a horizontal resolution of about 4 km. The model system includes nesting of sea ice. See more general information about the HYCOM model and TOPAZ4 in the Annex A.

The model uses the latest version 2.2 of the HYCOM model adapted to the NERSC interface, which includes the gridding by conformal mapping of Bentsen et al. (1999), the coupling to the EVP sea ice model as in Lisæter et al. (2003), the nesting procedures and input output. The grid size is 750 x 730 grid cells in the horizontal dimension and 28 hybrid (z-isopycnal) vertical layers. The upper 5 layers are imposed in z-coordinate space for best performance close to the surface. The model time steps are respectively 240 s and 6 s for the slow (baroclinic) and fast (barotropic) modes.

Figure 2 Surface currents in February 2008 (left) and July 2008 (right) in the TOPAZ4 model.

The vertical hybrid remapper is piecewise polynomial of 3rd order, WENO-type (Weighted Essentially Non-Oscillatory- Liu et al., 1994), which is a significant improvement over the piecewise constant method that was used in HYCOM v2.1. The advection of momentum is using a 2nd order numerical scheme with a relatively small deformation-dependent biharmonic viscosity factor of 0.2, the 4th order scheme used in Winther et al. (2006) is still under debugging in the version 2.2 of HYCOM and has not been used. The vertical mixing in the mixed layer is using the method from GISS described in Canuto et al. (2001, 2002).

In the present simulation, the tides are turned off and the water fluxes from the Baltic Sea in the Kattegatt is also turned off.

The models both use the GEBCO 1-minute digital bathymetry database averaged to the model grid. Both models are forced by operational weather analyses from the ECMWF at a resolution of 25 km. The surface winds (at 10 m) and the surface temperature and dew point temperatures at also taken at 2 m heights to compute the heat fluxes. A climatology of long-wave heat fluxes, cloud cover and precipitation is computed based on an average of the ERA-interim data. The same ERA-interim monthly average run-offs are fed into a hydrological model (TRIP, Oki and Sud 1998) to compute monthly river discharges all along the coasts of the two model domains. This strategy has been preferred to collecting river data since not all rivers flowing into the Nordic Seas from Norway, Iceland and Greenland are monitored. Additionally the nesting conditions include restoration to the GDEM V3.0 climatological salinity at the surface.

Since neither the TOPAZ4 nor NORDIC model include tides, the main difference resides only in horizontal resolution, otherwise the model code is the same, except that TOPAZ4 includes outflow from the Baltic Sea and has a latitude-dependent viscosity coefficient whereas NORDIC has a homogeneous viscosity.

The NORDIC model system is very CPU demanding. It was run on the NOTUR II facilities “Hexagon” – a 55 Tflop/s High Performance Computer Cray XT4 operated by Parallab, Bergen, using 166 CPUs, and takes 16 hours to simulate one year. For more technical details about how to integrate the HYCOM NORDIC model, we refer to the documentation “NERSC-HYCOM 2.2” by Knut A. Lisæter, Jan 2009.

In order to reduce the duration of model spin-up time, the NORDIC model has been initialized by horizontal interpolation of a well-balanced model field from the TOPAZ4 model and then run forward with lateral boundary conditions taken from the same TOPAZ4 model run. This ensures consistency between the initial and the lateral conditions. The NORDIC model has then been integrated over the period 2007 -2009 and the year 2008 has been retained for validation and analysis.

Figure 3: Schematic map of the surface currents in the Nordic Seas, courtesy from the PhD thesis of J. E. Ø. Nilsen, 2003, NERSC.

Ocean circulation

The TOPAZ4 surface currents in Figure 2 are monthly averages from February and July 2008. TOPAZ4 respects the classical picture of currents in the Nordic Seas with distinct branches of Atlantic Water inflow in the Iceland–Færoe and Færoe–Shetland channels (see Figure 3). The cyclonic surface circulation is well represented in both seasons and the topographic steering of the currents is obvious when compared to Figure 1. Note that the mesoscale features are not well resolved at this resolution in the Nordic Seas (although they are further South in the model domain). The wind forcing is visibly stronger in winter than in summer.

As depicted in Figure 3, the Nordic Seas receive water fluxes from the North Atlantic, the Arctic and the coasts. The North Atlantic Water (NAW), originating from the Gulf Stream, is warm and saline, and in all seasons can be characterized by a salinity above 35 psu. The colder and fresher Polar Waters (PW) enter through the Fram Strait in the Greenland Current but also through the Barents Sea and mix with NAW in the different sub-basins of the Nordic Seas. Deep mixing occurs in the winter, mostly in the Greenland Basin and form dense waters that overflow to the Irminger Sea through Denmark Strait and to the Irish Basin in the deeper parts of the Færoes Shetland Channel. Coastal waters have lower salinities due to the influence of rivers and form the Norwegian Coastal Current (NCC, flowing Northwards) and the East Greenland Coastal Current (EGCC, flowing Southwards).

Two images of the surface currents in the Greenland Sea of the nested NORDIC model are shown in Figure 4. The top panels show the sea ice thickness simulated by NORDIC. It shows that the ice is present in February in the Greenland and Irminger Sea, but not in July.

The NORDIC model, thanks to its higher resolution, distinguishes well the East Greenland Current (EGC) from the EGCC closer to the coast (lower panels). The EGC and EGCC are present in both seasons and bear abundant mesoscale features. Note that the Icelandic Coastal Current turning clockwise around Iceland seems stronger in winter, (Halldorsdottir et al., presented at the EGU, 2005). The resolution of both EGC and EGCC in the NORDIC model makes it relevant for studying the impact of ocean currents on the basal melt of the glaciers in Greenland, which are crucial for predicting the future sea level rise. Further North (middle row), the distinction between EGC and EGCC is only visible in the Summer as the surface currents are more driven by the sea ice in the Winter. In February, the simulation shows stronger currents along the ice edge and more homogeneous currents below the ice cover.

Figure 4 Sea ice thickness of the NORDIC model (top panels). Surface currents in the East Greenland Sea (middle panels) and Irminger Sea (lower panels) from the NORDIC model in February (left) and July (Right).

Figure 5: The trajectories of all of the NOAA AOML Drifting Buoy Data Assembly (DAC) Center's archived near-surface buoys, from 1978 to June, 2003, are shown as a "spaghetti" plot (source: RSMAS web site). The EGC and EGCC are clearly seen from the trajectories.

Figure 6: February temperatures at the surface (top) and at 100 m depths (bottom) in TOPAZ4 (left), NORDIC (middle) and difference TOPAZ4-minus-NORDIC (right).

Figure 7: Same as above for salinity

Effect of model resolution on the distribution of water masses

We will now compare the NORDIC high resolution model to the coarser TOPAZ4 model. The NORDIC model at 4 km grid resolves mesoscale eddies but TOPAZ4 does not with its 12 km grid. For applications that do not require information on mesoscale eddies, one may think that the coarse resolution is sufficient (ocean climate model usually have even coarser resolution of about 80 km). However, the net effect of mesoscale eddies does not average out on a long integration due to non-linear interactions between the mesoscale and large scale processes.

This is also evident on the water mass distributions: In Figure 6 the TOPAZ4 model is much warmer than NORDIC (up to 4 deg C) in the Norwegian and Lofoten basins. This indicates that the coarse resolution model is more diffusive and spreads the NAW broadly across the Norwegian Basin, North of the Feroes. This difference is equally visible at the surface and at 100 m depths but disappears at 700 m depths (not shown) because the NAW is a surface current. One interpretation is that the net effect of the eddies in the NORDIC model is to advect the warm waters closer to the Norwegian coast, but the higher resolution of the bathymetry in the critical Feroe-Shetland channel could also explain the different inflow of NAW in the Norwegian Sea. Further evaluation against satellite SST data, temperature and salinity profiles will show that the TOPAZ4 model is closer to reality than NORDIC, contrary to expectations. The differences in July are similar but slightly less pronounced than in February (not shown).

Figure 8: Left: NORDIC model SST in February (top) and July (bottom). Right: Satellite SST data from MODIS at the same dates. Satellite images processed by courtesy of A. Korosov, NERSC. The projection and colour scale are identical for model and satellite data.

The differences of salinity in Figure 7 are largest near the coast of Greenland where the TOPAZ4 model simulates water down to 2 psu fresher, with a larger difference at 100 m depths. The reason for that could be either a different transport in the EGC or the export of Arctic Sea ice through the Fram Strait.

Results from another nested HYCOM model of even higher resolution (3.5 km) in the Fram Strait have proven that the Southward export of sea ice through the Fram Strait was weaker with a higher resolution model (Results from the WIFAR project in the PETROMAKS programme). This could be explained by the average effect of mesoscale eddies on the drift of sea ice: the more turbulent eddying flow will on average slow down the Southward progression of the sea ice. The sea ice thus melts further South in a coarse resolution model than in an eddy-resolving model, which could explain the larger input of freshwater in the EGC and EGCC in TOPAZ4 than in NORDIC.

Validation against satellite SST data

The satellite SST data have not been assimilated in the ocean model and therefore represent completely independent data for validation. Figure 8 shows how the NORDIC model compares to Level-3 SST data at 4 km resolution from MODIS (freely available from the NASA website: <http://oceancolor.gsfc.nasa.gov/cgi/l3>, processed by courtesy of A. Korosov, NERSC). The MODIS satellite images are affected by cloud cover and are monthly

composites in order to remove the cloud mask. Note that the model SST is at the freezing point below sea ice while the satellite does not see below the ice. The sea ice mask and the remaining cloud mask are both in white in the satellite images.

The figure shows that the main distribution of warm and cold surface water masses in the Nordic Seas is correct. More detailed examination reveals the following:

- The two branches inflow of NAW between Iceland and the Færoes and between the Færoes and the Shetlands Islands are both well defined in the model.
- Further north the Norwegian Atlantic Current (NwAC) recirculation in the Lofoten Basin is weaker than seen in the SST image.
- The West Spitzbergen Current (WSC) – likely as a consequence of the above – is warmer in the NORDIC model than in satellite data.
- The recirculation waters of NAW in the Irminger Sea is warmer in NORDIC than in the satellite image. This is visible both in winter and in summer.
- The coastal waters around Iceland and Spitzbergen are too warm in the model, which may betray the absence of tides from the model.

Code	Area	Main source of data
Sq. 2	Northern North Sea / Norwegian Sea	IMR sections
Sq. 3	Norwegian Basin	Argo floats, Station M
Sq. 4	Lofoten Basin	Argo floats
Sq. 5	Fram Strait	AWI sections
Sq. 6	Fram Strait – Shallow Greenland side	Idem
Sq. 7	Fram Strait – Deep Greenland side	Idem
Sq. 8	Fram Strait – West Spitzbergen side	Idem
Sq. 1	Irminger Sea	Argo floats
Sub-division of Sq. 1	Vicinity of the Semilik Fjord	Field experiment

Table 1: Overview of selected regions for validation. Note that Sq. 5 encompasses Sq.6-8.

Validation against in-situ profiles in open ocean

Several sources are available for in-situ hydrographic profiles, the traditional field measurements from oceanographic repeat sections and the increasing popularity of autonomous Argo floats, drifting at their parking depth of 1500 m, taking a profile every ten days and transmitting the data in near-real time via satellite (<http://www.argo.ucsd.edu/>). The access to these data has been facilitated by NERSC participation to European projects from the 7th Framework Programme DAMOCLES (<http://www.damocles-eu.org/>) and MyOcean (<http://www.myocean.eu.org>). All such profiles are assembled internally at NERSC as part of the ArcWarm NFR project for climate studies and have been provided by A. Korablev (personal communication).

The data that were found most useful for the present study were the Fram Strait sections taken by Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI) in the DAMOCLES project, the Argo data taken from the CORIOLIS server at Ifremer and the repeat Fedje and Svinøy sections from the Institute of Marine Research (IMR). A last source of data was the samples taken by A. Korablev (personnal communication) near in the East Greenland Coast in the purpose of studying the freshwater outflow from the Greenland glaciers, funded by a private donation from Frank Mohn AS c/o Trond Mohn. The measured profiles are compared to the closest model grid point and linear interpolation is used in the vertical direction to project the model results from the hybrid coordinate to the measurement depths. The data analysis will proceed in selected

sub-regions of particular significance and follow the cyclonic circulation of the Nordic Seas from the North Sea to the Irminger Sea, turning clockwise as in Table 1.

Figure 9: Position of profiles in the Northern North Sea / Norwegian Sea.

Validation in the Northern North Sea / Norwegian Sea

The sampling in the North Sea and Southern Norwegian Sea is better in July than in February. The fit of temperature profiles is better for the NORDIC model than for TOPAZ4. In the latter, the transition between the mixed layer and the thermocline is too steep and confirms the difference visible in Figure 6: the TOPAZ4 model is too cold in the 100 m depths because of excessive horizontal diffusion and mixing with the cold PW. The thermocline and deeper waters however have the correct temperature, and the zero degrees isotherm at the correct depths, which is quite satisfactory. The salinity profiles are also acceptable and indicate the presence of NAW at a salinity superior to 35 psu, although the TOPAZ4 model may be slightly too fresh by 0.1 psu in the upper 300 m, this is corrected in the NORDIC model, but maybe for the wrong reason since the NORDIC model misses the freshwater input from the Baltic Sea. Note that in February, the NORDIC model seems also too saline in the upper water column. Both models simulate a halocline slightly too diffuse but the profiles reach the observations at depths deeper than 700 m, which is reassuring. The variability of profiles seems equivalent to the variability of observations in both models, indicating that the combined spatial and temporal variability within one month in Sq. 2 is realistic in the two models.

Figure 10: Temperature profiles in the Northern North Sea / Norwegian Sea in Feb and July 2008. Thin lines indicate individual profiles, thick lines are the average profiles for the region. Note that only shallow profiles were available in the winter.

Figure 11: Same as above for salinity. Note the vertical scale is different from the temperature profiles as they are flat in deep waters.

Figure 12: Position of all profiles in the Norwegian Basin

Validation in the Norwegian and Lofoten Basins

The Norwegian and Lofoten Basins holds a larger variety of waters indicated by the larger spread of profiles. A branch of NAW brings warm waters and salinities above 35 psu in the upper 600 m and PW are advected from the West, some mixing of the two water masses is evident from the spread in the profile plot. The TOPAZ4 system respects very well the average profile of temperature and the halocline is at the correct depths although the salinities are slightly offset towards more saline waters at all depths and the variability is underestimated. The reason why the offset affects only salinities but not temperature is unclear. The NORDIC model is both too cold (by up to 4 deg C) and too fresh (by 0.2 psu) in the upper 500 m, indicating that the NAW is too concentrated towards the Norwegian coast and too little mixed with the other resident water masses. This also indicates that the temperature difference between TOPAZ4 and NORDIC is surprisingly in the favour of TOPAZ4. The discrepancy between NORDIC and observations is most obvious in the winter, probably because of differences of sampling between summer and winter: profiles taken in February 2008 are located mostly the center of the Norwegian Basin (see Figure 12) and exaggerate a local problem.

Figure 13: Temperature profiles in the Norwegian Basin, left: February, Right: July.

Figure 14: Same as above for salinity profiles, note the vertical scales goes down to 1500 m instead of 2000 m.

Figure 15: Positions of profiles in the Greenland Basin.

Validation in the Greenland Basin

The Greenland Basin is an area of deep mixing and therefore exhibits an almost homogeneous water column with very little variability (only one of the Argo profiles in the box catches warm NAW). In the summer, a mix layer forms in the upper 50 m. Both the summer and winter profiles are well simulated by the two models although both tend to indicate temperature and salinity structures: TOPAZ4 at 200 m depths and NORDIC at 600 m depths. In the deeper waters, the models are slightly biased towards too warm (less than 0.5 deg) and too saline waters (less than 0.005 psu) but these differences are not large enough to be alarming.

Figure 16: Temperature profiles in the Greenland Basin.

Figure 17: Same as above for salinity profiles

Validation in the Fram Strait

The Fram Strait is the only deep water opening between the Arctic Ocean and the rest of the world oceans. It is therefore a natural choke point for the heat and salinity exchanges between the Arctic Ocean and Nordic Seas. This busy Strait is crossed by Polar Waters flowing southwards in the EGC on the Western side and crosses the last remnant of the Gulf Stream, the West Spitzberg Current (WSC) on the Eastern side. Parts of the WSC recirculate southwards in the middle of the Fram Strait. The Fram Strait has thus been split into three sub-boxes to analyse these currents separately. The Fram Strait is almost completely ice covered in the winter, with a large flux of thick multi-year ice exported from the Central Arctic into the Nordic Seas. This explains why there are almost no observations available in the winter. We will thus focus on the July 2008 data section taken by AWI.

Figure 18: Position of profiles in the Fram Strait

On the Western side of the Fram Strait, the TOPAZ4 model reproduces the temperature profile quite well and does particularly good job at reproducing the temperature maximum at

300 m depths made by Atlantic Waters. The NORDIC model is too cold between 100 m and 700 m depths and surprisingly misses the temperature maximum, as if the vertical mixing was excessive. In the center and on the Eastern side of the Fram Strait, on the contrary, the TOPAZ4 model seems to simulate a WSC too deep and carrying an excess of warm water. The NORDIC model respects the observations better, but still misses the thin layer of cold and fresh EGC on the top of the water column, which may also be a sign of excessive mixing. An insufficient inflow of EGC from the lateral boundary conditions to the North of the Fram Strait seems unlikely since the same TOPAZ4 system providing the lateral boundary conditions simulates the current structure correctly. The sea ice coverage has also been checked and fits reasonably well with satellite data from AMSR-E (not shown). This insufficient EGC in the NORDIC model needs therefore to be examined in more details. The salinity profiles in the WSC and the return current both show an excess of salinity (by 0.1 psu) in the two models, which is consistent with the excess of temperature (by 2 deg) also observed in the WSC.

Figure 19: Temperature profiles in the Fram Strait (West, center and East resp.). Data only available in July, but not in February.

Figure 20: Same as above for salinity profiles.

Validation in the Irminger Sea

The profiles in the Irminger Sea in February and July 2008 are mostly coming from Argo floats, a majority of them are taken in the EGC but in saline water recirculating from the Irminger Current. The summer temperature profile is well reproduced by all models but the models are too warm in the mixed layer in winter (NORDIC even more so than TOPAZ4, but still less than 1 deg off). The deep temperature profile is correct in both models. The spatial variability of the temperature profiles seems well reproduced in both models.

Figure 21: Profiles used in the Irminger Sea.

The salinity profile exhibits saline NAW in the top 500 m of water and a slightly fresher deep water (34.95 psu). In both seasons, the TOPAZ4 model seems to have too small vertical salinity gradients while the NORDIC model seems to exaggerate them. The EGC being both too warm and too saline is consistent with the insufficient EGC already mentioned in the Fram Strait (Sq. 6 above).

Figure 22: Temperature profiles in the Irminger Sea. Left: February 2008, Right: July 2008.

Figure 23: Same as above for salinity.

Figure 24: Position of the profiles taken by the Mohn-Sverdrup field experiment in August 2008

Validation in the vicinity of the Sermilik Fjord

A dedicated field experiment has taken place in the vicinity of the Sermilik Fjord in August 2008 to study the meltwater from the Greenland glacier. The data has been quality checked and provided by A. Korablev (personal communication). The observations are compared to the closest model grid point, which is never further than 4 km in the NORDIC model but could be located at a longer distance in the TOPAZ4 model (about 12 km). This must be kept in mind when looking at the profiles taken closest to the coast, namely in the box Sq. 4 in Figure 24.

Consistently with the above validation in the Fram Strait and Irminger Sea, the NORDIC model seems to lack some inflow from the EGC and the TOPAZ4 system therefore seems closer to observations. However an closer look at the upper part of the profiles reveals that the near-surface slopes and the vertical position of the temperature maximum are more correct in NORDIC than in TOPAZ4 in spite of the offset in temperature and salinity. This indicates that the vertical mixing is better simulated in NORDIC than in TOPAZ4.

Figure 25: Temperature and salinity profiles in the sub-squares 2-3-4 near Sermilik Fjord

Figure 26: Temperature and salinity profiles in sub-squares 5 and 6 near Semilik Fjord

Conclusion and continuation plan

The validation of the TOPAZ4 and NORDIC models in the year 2008 reveals an overall good representation of the large scale and local currents although some deficiencies have been observed. The increase of horizontal resolution helps simulating the vertical structure of the water in the Northern North Sea. But further North the NwAC recirculation in the Lofoten Basin is insufficient in the NORDIC model and the thermal structure is better simulated in the TOPAZ4 system, although maybe for the wrong reason (more horizontal diffusion which may compensate for the lack of recirculation). The EGC simulated by the NORDIC model does not transport enough cold and fresh water near the surface, which seems to affect the results all along the Greenland Sea and even as far as the Irminger Sea. The excess of warm NAW recirculation into the Irminger Sea could also be explained by the insufficient EGC as a stronger EGC would have blocked this recirculation. In all of these latter aspects, the TOPAZ4 system surprisingly seems more realistic than NORDIC, in spite of its coarser resolution.

However, the known deficiencies of the NORDIC model setup (i.e. the absence of fluxes from the Baltic Sea and the absence of tides) do not appear as clear responsible for the discrepancies with observations, which could indicate a possible error at the Northern and Southern lateral boundary of the model. For instance, insufficient coverage of sea ice could result in the same excessive vertical mixing as experienced in the Fram Strait and should be validated in more details.

In spite of these deficiencies, it is also found that the processes simulated by the NORDIC model are overall correctly reproducing the observations. Then once the above deficiencies are corrected, the model will be fit for different oceanographic studies of the Nordic Seas, for example the generation of eddies on the steep ridges between the Lofoten and Greenland Basins, their contribution to the cyclonic gyre circulation in the Nordic Seas (Köhl, 2007, Gascard and Mork, 2008), but also Lagrangian tracer simulations (Samuelson et al. 2009), studying the interactions of the ocean with the Greenland glaciers, studying the transformations of water masses in the Nordic Seas, and the impact of mesoscale activity on the primary production, following the studies of Hansen et al. (2009, 2010).

Data assimilation of satellite and in-situ data could eventually be applied as in Counillon and Bertino (2009) in order to get mesoscale features at the correct place and correct time, i.e. for obtaining an accurate history of the circulation in the Nordic Seas.

Appendix A Technical details of numerical model formulation

The HYCOM model

Ocean general circulation models have traditionally been classified based on their vertical representation. These include the discretization in z-level co-ordinates, terrain-following σ -co-ordinates, and isopycnal models, which use density as the vertical co-ordinate. Each of these models has advantages and disadvantages depending on their applications, and there is now a consensus that a “hybrid” model combining the best parts from all of these will be the model for the future. Ideally, an ocean model should: retain water mass characteristics for centuries of integration (a characteristic of isopycnic co-ordinates); have high vertical resolution in the surface mixed layer for proper representation of thermodynamic and biochemical processes (a characteristic of z-level co-ordinates); maintain sufficient vertical resolution in unstratified or weakly-stratified regions of the ocean; and have high vertical resolution in coastal regions (a characteristic of terrain-following co-ordinates). The hybrid co-ordinate is isopycnal in the open, stratified ocean, but smoothly reverts to a terrain following co-ordinate in shallow coastal regions, and to a z-level co-ordinate in the mixed layer and/or unstratified seas. The hybrid co-ordinate extends the geographic range of applicability of traditional isopycnic co-ordinate circulation models into shallow coastal seas and unstratified parts of the world ocean. In doing so, the model combines the advantages of the different types of co-ordinates to optimally simulate both coastal and open-ocean circulation features. Such a model, i.e., the Hybrid Co-ordinate Ocean Model (HYCOM) has recently been developed by Bleck (2002), based on the previous Miami Isopycnal Co-ordinate Ocean Model (MICOM) by Bleck et al. (1992). This latest HYCOM model is adopted in this study.

Vertical co-ordinate scheme

The vertical movement of water masses can be divided into a Lagrangian movement, where a co-ordinate surface is moving with the water in the vertical, as in an isopycnal model, and the movement of water through the co-ordinate surface as is done in all models with a fixed vertical co-ordinate system, e.g. z-level models and σ -co-ordinate models. HYCOM includes both representations of vertical movement of water masses and allows for a combined use of material co-ordinate surfaces and fixed co-ordinate surfaces.

The algorithm exploits the fact that all layers have an assigned reference density (as in isopycnal models). Further, one defines a minimum layer thickness for all layers except for the deep layers intersecting the bathymetry. Whenever the upper isopycnal layer approaches this minimum thickness, because water with this reference density ceases to exist in a vertical column, this layer is used as a vertical level co-ordinate providing resolution in the mixed layer. Further, this level co-ordinate is located at a depth according to a predefined rule. The algorithm results in a stack of levels located from the surface and downwards with a specified resolution. As a consequence, the model allows for arbitrary high vertical resolution near the surface by adding a sufficient number of light (and therefore always mass less) layers to the model.

Thus to summarize, based on the number of layers defined and their chosen reference densities, the layers will distribute themselves in the vertical, starting with isopycnal layers from the sea floor and upwards towards the surface. The layers with reference densities lighter than the existing water masses in the present water-column will be stacked from the

surface, downwards with a specified vertical resolution, and used as z-level or σ -level coordinates.

Mixing processes in HYCOM

Vertical mixing in HYCOM is a combination of cabbeling, restoration processes and the explicitly prescribed physical mixing. The horizontal advection and mixing of layer thicknesses, tracers and momentum is computed using two-dimensional algorithms operating on individual layers (as is also done in MICOM). However, the advection of layer thicknesses in the continuity equation will introduce a vertical movement of the layer interfaces, also among the level co-ordinates near the surface. Further, horizontal diffusion of temperature and salinity in an isopycnic layer may lead to a deviation from the reference density. The non-linearity of the equation of state implies that the mixing of two water masses with different temperature and salinity properties but the same density may result in a new water mass with a different density.

The prescribed vertical mixing is solved using the GISS vertical turbulence closure scheme developed by Canuto et al. (2001, 2002). The scheme computes the vertical mixing coefficient over a vertical column in the model, and takes into account the effect of wind induced, mixed layer turbulence and additional mixing parameterisations for processes such as internal wave breaking, Richardson dependent vertical current shear, salt fingering and double diffusion. A background vertical mixing coefficient ensures the presence of a low diapycnal diffusion in the deep ocean. The scheme uses an algorithm to compute the vertical diffusivity in a water column, and thereafter a one-dimensional diffusion equation is solved for temperature, salinity and momentum.

At each time step, an algorithm restores the correct location of the co-ordinate surfaces. Among the isopycnal layers in the deep ocean there is a restoration towards reference densities, an effect called cabbeling, where a small amount of water is mixed between adjacent layers to restore the reference densities. For the level co-ordinates near the surface, water is moved/mixed between layers to restore the layer interfaces to their predefined locations in depth. This process is designed to conserve temperature, salinity and momentum in a water column.

Figure A1. Nesting models, example in the Barents Sea. The red rectangle indicates the nested model boundaries. Note the fine structures in the inner model.

Sea ice model

The sea ice model coupled to the NERSC HYCOM model is a dynamic – thermodynamic model.

The ice thermodynamics model used has many features in common with the 0-layer ice thermodynamic formulation of Semtner (1976), which ignores the specific heat of the ice. In the limit of zero heat capacity of ice the heat conduction equation gives the vertical temperature profile in the ice as a linear function. The conductive heat flux has, as a result of this, the same absolute value at the surface and bottom of the ice slab. The thermodynamic model also includes a snow layer, and a linear temperature profile is prescribed through the snow as well. The model is a two-category ice model, meaning that a model grid cell consists of a fraction of open water, and a fraction of ice with a prognostic ice thickness. The present model uses a simplified formulation of heat exchange using so-called infinite diffusivity. In this formulation, any heat available for sea ice melt in the upper ocean layer is immediately used to melt ice. The available heat is determined by the upper ocean layer temperature deviation from the freezing point of the ocean. One consequence of this is that no ice will be present in a model grid cell when the sea-surface temperature is above the freezing point of the ocean. For full details of the ice-thermodynamic model we refer to Drange and Simonsen (1996).

The ice dynamics model is the elastic-viscous-plastic (EVP) ice rheology of Hunke and Dukowicz (1997). The EVP model presents an alternative to solving the traditional viscous-plastic model (VP; Hibler 1979) by introducing an elastic component to the rheology equations. The elastic waves dampen out when solving the dynamical equations, and the resulting solution approaches the one obtained by the VP model. The benefits of the EVP rheology is that it allows for an explicit parallel solution of the VP equations. The numerical implementation of the EVP model also shows better response to rapid changes in forcing of the sea ice component, relative to numerical implementations of the VP model (Hunke and Dukowicz 1997).

The ice dynamic and thermodynamic models have been solved for the same model grid (Arakawa C-grid) as the ocean model. The advection of sea ice properties (concentrations, thickness and snow depth) is following the WENO3 scheme (Liu et al., 1994, from I. Bethke's MICOM implementation at BCCR, Bergen).

Nesting Procedures

Open boundary conditions and nesting in ocean circulation models is complex. The main problem is that for a model with open boundaries, the number of boundary conditions is dependent on the structure of the flow field penetrating the boundary. There are actually four cases that must be considered, i.e., inflow or outflow and for each of these one can have supersonic or subsonic velocities. To avoid dealing with the problem of exactly specifying the boundary conditions in an "exact" nesting scheme, most approaches use some kind of boundary relaxation towards the outer model solution. Figure A1 illustrates the nesting from a low-resolution North Atlantic and Arctic model (TOPAZ1 with a horizontal resolution of 25 km) to a high-resolution (4.5 km) model of the Barents Sea. Both the ocean and sea ice parameters are used for forcing the local model.

This results in what is termed one way nesting schemes, where the boundary conditions of the regional model are relaxed towards the output from a coarser large scale model. For the slowly varying variables, i.e., baroclinic velocities, temperature, salinity and layer interfaces, this is a fully appropriate way to include the boundary conditions. For the barotropic variables the relaxation approach requires careful tuning to avoid reflection of waves at the open model boundaries. In HYCOM the barotropic model is a hyperbolic wave equation for pressure and vertically integrated velocities. Following an approach outlined by Browning and Kreiss (1982, 1986), it is possible to compute the barotropic boundary conditions exactly, while taking into consideration both the waves propagating into the regional model from the external solution and the waves propagating out through the boundary from the regional model. The scheme has been tested extensively and has not yet shown problematic behaviour. In addition, it also made it fairly simple to include the tidal forcing on the barotropic mode.

The practical implementation of the nesting scheme is based on communication through files stored on disk. The outer model dumps the solution interpolated to grid points in the relaxation zone of the regional model every six hours. For the baroclinic mode, which only changes slowly, this is considered to be high resolution in time. It should also be sufficient for the barotropic mode since the outer model does not contain tides. The regional model reads the files every six hours and uses interpolation in time to specify the relaxation boundary conditions at every time step. The communication between the grids is general and there is no restriction on the relative orientation or resolution of the grids.

Rivers

The Norwegian and Greenland rivers are very important for the sea ice and ocean circulation. River outflows are based on monthly climatologies using the discharges from the ERA-I reanalysis, fed into the global hydrological model from Oki and Sud (1998) and verified against discharges from the literature. Rivers are placed on the grid point on the domain closest to where the river fluxes were measured.

Spatial and temporal resolution of input data

1. The **ECMWF ERA-Interim atmospheric forecast** with 1/4th -degree horizontal resolution and 6-hours time steps.

2. The TOPAZ4 **lateral boundary conditions** have resolution ca. 12 km and temporal resolution of 6 hours.

Bathymetry

The model bathymetry is based on the GEBCO 1-minute database. Little smoothing is required since HYCOM is not subject to pressure gradient errors on steep topography. More precise topographic data can easily be adapted if provided externally.

The model depths will be added to the output database.

Figure A2. The domain of the large scale TOPAZ4 model of the North Atlantic and Arctic. A snapshot of sea surface heights is shown.

The TOPAZ4 North Atlantic and Arctic model

Description

To achieve nesting conditions, a large scale model of the Arctic and North Atlantic Ocean is required that simulates the exchanges between the Arctic and North East Atlantic through the Canadian Archipelago. The model domain does not cover the Pacific Ocean South of Bering Strait (see the model domain illustrated in Figure A2). The southern border of the domain is set South of the Equator. The horizontal grid is 800 × 880 grid cells and a resolution that varies from 11 km in the Arctic to 16 km in the North Atlantic. The total number of layers in the vertical is 28, with a linear increase in density in the first ten layers and an exponential increase in the last twelve layers. The density range covers fresh coastal waters until dense waters of the deep Arctic with a maximum density of 1.02813.

The model has open boundaries in the Bering Strait with a yearly barotropic flux of 0.8 Sv from the Pacific to the Arctic (following Woodgate *et al.* 2010), and an open boundary in the Atlantic South of the Equator. Along the two boundaries, salinity and temperature are relaxed to the GDEM climatology. The Southern boundary is far from the area of interest, and will not have any influence on the nested model. The boundary in Bering Strait is closer but its representation is expected to be realistic enough for the Nordic Seas. The GDEM climatology is also used to initialize the model, for relaxation of surface temperature and salinities and for the bottom pressures. These are used when we start the spin-up of the model, initialized in 1973.

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